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FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF REPRESENTATION AND DISTRIBUTION OF THE MEANING IN CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the intricate relationship between representation and the distribution of meaning within various contexts through a functional analysis framework. By examining how meaning is constructed and communicated across different linguistic and cultural settings, key factors that influence interpretation and understanding are identified. The study aims at utilizing case studies from literature, media, and everyday communication to illustrate how context shapes the representation of ideas and emotions. It is revealed that meaning is not static but rather dynamic, influenced by social, cultural, and situational variables.

Key words: context, meaning, realization, concept, culture, distribution, semantics, pragmatics

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ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИИ И РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ЗНАЧЕНИЯ В КОНТЕКСТЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Эта статья посвящена сложной взаимосвязи между представлением и распределением значения в различных контекстах с помощью функционального анализа. Исследуя, как создается значение и передается информация в различных языковых и культурных условиях, мы выявляем ключевые факторы, влияющие на интерпретацию и понимание. Цель исследования - использовать примеры из литературы, средств массовой информации и повседневного общения, чтобы проиллюстрировать, как контекст формирует представление идей и эмоций. Показано, что значение не статично, а, скорее, динамично и зависит от социальных, культурных и ситуативных переменных.

Ключевые слова: контекст, значение, реализация, концепт, культура, распространение, семантика, прагматика

Abdullayeva Shahnoza Rahimjon qizi
O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti

KONTEKSTDA MA'NONI IFODALASH VA TAQSIMLASHNING FUNKTSIONAL TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola funktsional tahlil doirasi orqali turli kontekstlarda ma'noni aks ettirish va uning taqsimoti o'rtasidagi murakkab munosabatlarni ko'rib chiqadi. Turli xil lingvistik va madaniy sharoitlarda ma'no qanday tuzilishi va yetkazilishini o'rganish orqali talqin va tushunishga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy omillar aniqlanadi. Tadqiqot kontekst g'oyalari va hissiyotlarni qanday shakllantirishini tasvirlash uchun adabiyot, ommaviy axborot vositalari va kundalik muloqotdan amaliy tadqiqotlardan foydalanishga qaratilgan. Ma'no statik emas, balki dinamik, ijtimoiy, madaniy va vaziyat o'zgaruvchilari ta'sirida ekanligi aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: kontekst, ma'no, anglash, tushuncha, madaniyat, tarqatish, semantika, pragmatika

INTRODUCTION (ВВЕДЕНИЕ/KIRISH)

From the linguistic point of view, the concept “**context**” is considered to be a frame surrounding any event, it serves as a resource to interpretate the event appropriately. In other words, while analyzing what a word, a phrase, a sentence means, the information and situation surrounding them play a significant role to have a clear understanding and this very issue is “context” in Linguistics. A range of factors can be included in a context and they are as following: physical setting, cultural background, participants, voice tone, or previous discourse. It is important to understand the context in order to have a clear, accurate language interpretation, simply because words, phrases, sentences mean differently depending on the context they are used in.

Regarding “**meaning**” in Linguistics, it is the information, emotions, ideas, intentions which are conveyed through the language usage.

The representation of meaning is how language encodes and represents concepts, ideas, and relationships between them. It examines the relationship between linguistic signs (such as words, phrases, and sentences) and the meanings they convey. To be more precise, the linguistic meaning of “representation” is how languages produce meaning. It includes how information is conveyed through language, and the role of words, phrases and sentences in the construction of the meaning. **Meaning is not fixed**, but varies depending on the specific context. In different contexts, one word may mean different notions, as a result.

MATERIALS AND METHODS (ЛИТЕРАТУРА И МЕТОД/ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METOD)

Distribution of meaning in context.

Regarding the distribution of meaning in context, it deals with the way a meaning is organized and distributed using particular linguistic elements like words, phrases, and sentences and how applying these elements influence the meaning interpreted. In short, the difference between representation and distribution of the meaning in context is that the former involves the construction of meaning through language while the latter explores how various language units are applied in particular contexts and their effect on the meaning interpretation.

One of the most common concepts in meaning representation in context is **semantic meaning**. Generally, semantic meaning refers to the meaning of words and phrases regardless of how they are used. “a dog”, for example, has a special meaning that is typically understood as a small domesticated carnivorous mammal. Lexical resources, such as dictionaries and semantic networks, can be used to represent this semantic meaning.

Context, however, can change the meaning of words and phrases. There are a few key aspects to take into consideration while representing and distributing the meaning in context, one of which is **Contextual Meaning**. The meaning of words and phrases can vary based on the context in which they are used. The intended meaning might be inferred from the context, for instance, that the word “course” can refer to both the route or direction followed by a ship, aircraft, road, or a river and a dish, or a set of dishes served together, forming one of the successive parts of a meal. Another aspect to consider is Pragmatics which studies how speakers use a language so that communicative goals can be achieved. Beyond literal interpretation, it involves understanding how speakers use language for conveying meaning. Taking the sentence “I saw a dog” as an example, the meaning of the word

“dog” in this sentence is influenced by the context in which it is used. Depending on the linguistic environment, it might refer to a specific cat seen recently by the speaker or to cats in general. In most cases, pragmatic meaning is used to refer to this contextual meaning, that is, (around 70%) **pragmatic meaning=contextual meaning**.

DISCUSSION (ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ/МУХОКАМА)

Generally, the realization of concepts in Linguistics means how abstract ideas, meanings are expressed in language. To be more precise, what kind of words, phrases are chosen to deliver what is meant by a concept or how ideas are structured and arranged, and it also refers to how speakers and listeners understand, interpret them. Concept realization is closely connected with semantics, the study of meaning in Linguistics. This is because, comprehending the way concepts are expressed in language can offer valuable perspectives on the way speakers formulate and convey ideas, as well as how language influences our perception of reality.

As is already discussed, the realization of concepts refers to how abstract ideas, categories, or relationships are expressed and represented in language. Different languages have unique ways of realizing concepts, which can influence the structure, grammar, and vocabulary of the language. Some common forms of realization of concepts in linguistics include:

1. Morphology: Morphology is the study of word structure and formation. Languages may use different morphological processes, such as affixation (adding prefixes or suffixes), compounding (combining multiple words), or internal modification (changing internal sounds or letters) to express concepts. For example, English uses plural suffixes (-s, -es) to indicate more than one of something (e.g., "cat" becomes "cats").
2. Syntax: Syntax refers to the rules governing the arrangement of words in a sentence to convey meaning. Different languages have different word order patterns (e.g., subject-verb-object in English vs. subject-object-verb in Japanese) and syntactic structures to express concepts such as tense, aspect, mood, and agreement.
3. Semantics: Semantics is the study of meaning in language. Languages use various semantic strategies, such as lexical distinctions (different words for similar concepts), metaphors, idioms, and collocations, to express nuanced meanings and relationships between concepts.
4. Pragmatics: Pragmatics is the study of how language is used in context to achieve communicative goals. Languages may have different pragmatic conventions for expressing politeness, social status, and interpersonal relationships through language, as well as for interpreting non-literal meanings (e.g., sarcasm, irony).
5. Phonology: Phonology is the study of sound patterns in language. Different languages have distinct phonological systems that determine how sounds are organized and combined to form words and convey meaning. Phonological features such as tone, stress, and intonation can be used to distinguish words and express grammatical distinctions.

RESULTS (РЕЗУЛТАТЫ/НАТИЖАЛАР)

While conceptual meaning is being represented, different factors are involved. They are as following:

- The linguistic context- words or phrases surrounding a specific word
- The situational context-the physical settings, participants, and shared knowledge
- The social context-the social roles, relationships, and participants' cultural norms.

To have a better understanding, let's see and analyze a few examples below.

- 1) “My neighbor is cool”

In a literal sense, the word “cool” can refer to a temperature that is neither hot nor cold. “Cool” is an informal term to describe someone who is stylish, calm, relaxed, or of high social standing.

- 2) “That is sick”

Literally, the term “sick” means being ill or unwell. According to conceptual meaning, mostly used by younger generation, the word “sick” is used to refer to the meaning “impressive, amazing, or cool”

- 3) “The hot dog is on fire”

According to its literal definition, it means that the hot dog is burning, indeed while in a humorous context it refers to its incredibly tasty flavor.

4) "I love you"

Romantic-emotional attachment or affection.

Friendship-to convey closeness, no romantic meaning

5) "Run"

Literally, it is the act of swiftly moving on foot whereas in a figurative sense, "run" refers to managing or operating something, such as a business or a computer program. "Your dad runs a business of his own." Sounds cool, doesn't it?

6) "Bank"

- The term "bank" refers to a financial institution where people deposit, withdraw, and manage their funds.
- As a geographical term, "bank" refers to the side of a river.
- As a gaming term, the term "bank" refers to a reserve of points or resources.

7) "Crane"

- The literal meaning of the word "crane" is a large and tall bird with a long neck and long legs.
- Cranes are large machines used for lifting and moving heavy objects in an industrial setting.

8) "Pitch"

- A pitch, in its literal sense, refers to a sticky, dark substance or the act of throwing something.
- In the context of sports, "pitch" refers to the playing field, such as a soccer or baseball field.
- Business pitches refer to presentations that are intended to sell products or ideas.

9) "Rock" "Rock" in geology refers to a solid mineral substance that makes up the crust of the Earth. When used in a musical context, the term "rock" designates a popular music style distinguished by an intense beat and electric guitars.

10) "Energy"

"Energy" can be used to describe vigor or enthusiasm in ordinary speech.

The ability of a physical system to perform an action or bring about a change is referred to as "energy" in physics. It can take on different forms, including thermal, potential, and kinetic energy.

CONCLUSION (ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ XULOSA)

Overall, the forms of realization, distribution of concepts in linguistics encompass a wide range of linguistic phenomena that reflect how language structure and convey information about the world around us.

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